

Graphs with the golden ratio eigenvalues and conjugated π -systems

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Abstract: Molecular graphs of π -conjugated systems having the golden ratio, $\phi = 1.6180339\dots$ and the golden ratio conjugate, $1/\phi = 0.6180339\dots$ as eigenvalues are identified. The smallest possible connected graph having such eigenvalues is a two-vertex graph with one vertex of weight $+1$ or -1 . Real π -systems that have been identified are (i) butadiene, (ii) unbranched polyenes, (iii) radialenes and (iv) π -systems represented by comb-like graphs; all of them have $\pm\phi$ and $\pm 1/\phi$ as four eigenvalues. Two series of IPR fullerenes have been found which contain $-1\pm\phi$ and $-1\pm 1/\phi$ in their eigenspectra. Some special π -conjugated molecules which are outside these categories have also been found.

Keywords: Graphs, eigenspectra, golden ratio, mirror plane fragmentation, dendralene, IPR fullerene.

Introduction

The Fibonacci sequence^{1,2} of numbers

$$1, 1, 2, 3, 5, 8, 13, 21, \dots$$

is one in which every number (excepting the first two) is the sum of the previous two numbers. A Fibonacci number (F_n) is defined by the recurrence relation

$$\begin{aligned} F_n &= F_{n-1} + F_{n-2} \quad (n \geq 2) \\ F_0 &= 1, \quad F_1 = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

It was shown long ago^{3,4} by Johannes Kepler that with increase in n the ratio of two successive Fibonacci numbers converges to a transcendental number (ϕ):

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F_n}{F_{n-1}} = \phi = 1.6180339887\dots \quad (2)$$

The following is the analytical expression^{3,4} for ϕ :

$$\phi = \frac{\sqrt{5} - 1}{2} \quad (3)$$

Owing to the occurrence of this ratio in numerous fields such as architecture, geometry, physics, mathematics, botany, physiology, etc., ϕ is called the 'Golden ratio' (or, sometimes the 'Golden mean'). The inverse of the ratio is just 1 less than itself and

is called the 'golden ratio conjugate':

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\phi} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{F_{n-1}}{F_n} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5} - 1} \\ &= 0.6180339887\dots = \phi - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Graph theoretical aspects of the Fibonacci numbers were pointed out by Hosoya^{5,6} in terms of the topological index Z . This index is the sum of all k -matching numbers i.e. the number of ways of choosing k disjoint edges (bonds) from a given graph; it brings out the topological nature of graphs representing the carbon atom skeleton of hydrocarbon molecules⁷⁻⁹. A class of polynuclear aromatic hydrocarbons (with zig-zag chains of fused rings) have been identified and termed 'Fibonacenes'^{10,11} owing to the fact that their Kekule' structure counts coincide with Fibonacci numbers. More recently, some graph theoretical aspects of the golden ratio have been discovered¹² and the 'golden family graphs' have been defined; in the sequence of graphs in this family, the Z values of the graphs occur in the Fibonacci (or, a related) sequence and consequently the ratio of the Z -values converges to the golden ratio. Examples of two series of graphs of such golden family are shown in Fig. 1. There are some scanty reports^{13,14} on graphs having the golden ratio and its conjugate in their eigenspectra; how-

Fig. 1. Some examples of golden family graphs with Z-values converging to the golden ratio.

ever, to our knowledge so far, there is no report on the occurrence of this ratio in the eigenspectra of chemical graphs. The objective of the present work is to search for π -conjugated systems whose molecular graphs have $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$, in their eigenspectra. The smallest possible (weighted) graph with such eigenvalues has been found out first. Then by utilizing the McClelland algorithm of mirror plane fragmentation^{15,16}, real π -systems with such eigenvalues have been searched for.

Mirror-plane fragmentation of graphs

In graph theory the lengths of the edges (bonds) and inter-bond angles have no relevance – only the connectivities of the graphs are important. But still, one can imagine a plane (σ) through the graph such that vertices on one side of the plane are topologically similar to those on the other side of σ . A scheme was proposed by McClelland^{15,16} for splitting graphs by means such “symmetry” planes into fragments such that the union of the eigenspectra of the fragment graphs is the eigenspectrum of the whole graph. Mathematical justification of such fragmentation on the basis of vertex adjacencies was given later¹⁷. In brief, the scheme can be stated as follows:

(i) The symmetry plane (σ) divides a graph G into two fragments, G^+ and G^- .

(ii) The component graphs are drawn by deleting those edges of G through which σ passes.

(iii) Vertices on the plane of symmetry are included in the fragment G^+ .

(iv) The weight of the edge between a vertex ly-

ing on the plane of symmetry and a vertex not on the plane but in the fragment G^+ is multiplied by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$.

The image of this edge on other side of σ is deleted.

(v) If σ bisects an edge of weight k which originally connected the vertices v_i and v_j then the vertex-weight of v_i in G^+ is increased by k and that of v_j in G^- is decreased by k .

The smallest connected vertex-weighted graph with the golden ratio eigenvalues

A trivial result in the search for graphs with golden ratio eigenvalues is a completely disconnected graph with four vertices carrying weights $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$. This is of no consequence in the present analysis. However, the characteristic polynomial (CP) of the graph G_1 (Fig. 2) is

$$P(G_1; x) = x(x-h) - 1 = x^2 - hx - 1 \quad (5)$$

For $h = 1$ the zeroes of this CP are $(1 \pm \sqrt{5})/2 = \phi, 1/\phi$

For $h = -1$ the zeroes of this CP are $(1 \pm \sqrt{5})/2 = \phi, 1/\phi$.

Hence G_1 represents the smallest possible golden ratio

Fig. 2. The smallest connected vertex-weighted graph with eigenvalues $-\phi, -1/\phi$.

graphs with $h = 1$ and -1 . However it does not represent any real molecule.

Butadiene

The molecular graph of butadiene is a simple linear chain (L_4) with four vertices. Its mirror plane fragments are exactly G_1 with $h = -1$ and 1 (Fig. 3). Hence butadiene is a π -conjugated system with eigenvalues (HMO energies) $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$ ($= \pm 1.618$, ± 0.618) which are \pm pairs of the golden ratio and its conjugate. Many graphs contain L_4 as a mirror plane fragment and consequently have the four golden ratio eigenvalues. Some important classes of such graphs are discussed in the following sections.

Unbranched polyenes:

An unbranched π -conjugated hydrocarbon with n carbon atoms is represented by a linear chain L_n as the molecular (H-suppressed) graph. It is easy to recognize (Fig. 4) that in the series of graphs

$L_4, L_9, L_{19}, L_{39}, \dots$

any member contains its previous member as a mirror plane fragment. Hence by a progressive application of the McClelland algorithm all the graphs in the above series are found to contain L_4 as a mirror plane fragment, and consequently have $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$ in their eigenspectra.

Dendralenes:

When a pendant vertex is attached to each vertex of a linear chain (L_n) the resulting graph, denoted by $L_n + n(p)$ is comb-like (Fig. 5). They represent conjugated π -systems called 'dendralenes'. Important properties of these cross-conjugated systems have been studied graph theoretically in a number of works¹⁸⁻²⁰. Such graphs were classified as a type of 'reciprocal graphs'²¹ whose eigenspectra are composed of pairs of eigenvalues of the form $\pm\lambda$, $\pm 1/\lambda$. They represent a special type of polyenes, two

Fig. 3. Mirror-plane fragmentation of the butadiene graph (L_4).

Fig. 4. Mirror-plane fragmentation of L_9 and L_{19} (L_n means a linear n -vertex chain with one terminal edge of weight $\sqrt{2}$).

Fig. 5. Two examples of π -conjugated hydrocarbons having graphs of the type $L_n + n(p)$.

examples being shown in Fig. 6. A mirror plane fragment of $L_5 + 5(p)$ is the butadiene graph, $L_2 + 2(p) \equiv L_4$; similarly, $L_{11} + 11(p)$ has $L_5 + 5(p)$ as a fragment, which, in turn, has $L_2 + 2(p)$ or L_4 as a fragment (Fig. 6). In this way, each graph in the sequence

$L_2 + 2(p)$, $L_5 + 5(p)$, $L_{11} + 11(p)$, $L_{23} + 23(p)$,

has its previous graph as a mirror plane fragment and all the graphs in the sequence has the four eigenvalues $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$ in their eigenspectra.

Annulenes:

Molecular graphs for annulenes with n carbon

atoms are cycles (C_n) with n vertices. As shown in Fig. 7, the smallest cycle having L_4 as a mirror-plane fragment is C_{10} . The cycle C_{20} has L_9 as a mirror-plane fragment and the latter has L_4 as a fragment. In this way, each member of the series of cycles C_{10} , C_{20} , C_{40} , C_{80} ,

Radialenes:

$[n]$ Radialenes (or, $[n]$ methylenecycloalkanes) are conjugated hydrocarbons containing n -membered rings of sp^2 -hybridized C-atoms, to each of which a $=CH_2$ group is attached. It has been shown graph theoretically²⁰ that radialenes (and dendralenes) are important in the design of conducting and ferromagnetic polymers. Molecular graphs of radialenes are cycles each vertex of which is attached to one pedant vertex and are denoted by $C_n + n(p)$. Examples are given in Fig. 8. The only chemically significant radialene which has L_4 as a fragment is $C_6 + 6(p)$, i.e. hexamethylene cyclohexane (Fig. 8).

Linear polyacenes:

Naphthalene, a linear polyacene with two rings, $(LP)_2$, has L_4 as a mirror plane fragment. Similarly $(LP)_5$ has $(LP)_2$ as a fragment (Fig. 9). In this way, in the sequence

$(LP)_2$, $(LP)_5$, $(LP)_{11}$, $(LP)_{23}$,

each member has its previous member as a fragment

Fig. 6. Mirror-plane fragmentation of $L_5 + 5(p)$ and $L_{11} + 11(p)$.

Fig. 7. Mirror-plane fragmentation of the cycle graphs C_{10} , C_{20} and C_{40} .

and all members contain L_4 as a common fragment with eigenvalues $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$.

IPR fullerenes:

Carbon cages in which all 12 pentagons are isolated by intervening hexagons are called IPR fullerenes²²⁻²⁴. Two series of such fullerenes having general formula C_{50+10N} and C_{60+12N} were discussed

earlier²⁵ and it was shown that their non-degenerate eigenvalues could be obtained by using 5-fold and 6-fold rotational symmetry after constructing a generic graph (G) of the type shown in Fig. 10. It has $10 + 2N$ vertices (for each series) and its right hand mirror plane fragment is a linear chain (L^-) with $(10 + 2N - 4)/2 = 3 + N$ vertices; however, every vertex of this fragment (L^-) has a weight of -1 . General

Fig. 8. Molecular graphs of two example radialenes.

Fig. 9. Mirror-plane fragmentation of linear polyacenes $(LP)_n$.

formula for eigenvalues of this weighted linear chain is

$$\lambda_j = -1 + 2\cos [j\pi/(N+4)],$$

$$j = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, 3+N \quad (6)$$

The IPR fullerenes C_{60} , C_{70} , C_{80} , be-

Fig. 10. The generic graph (G_A) and its fragments giving the common eigenvalues of C_{50+10N} and C_{60+12N} IPR fullerenes.

long to the series C_{50+10N} while C_{72} , C_{84} , C_{96} , belong to the series C_{60+12N} . The eigenvalues $\pm\phi$, $\pm 1/\phi$ occur in the eigenspectra of the unweighted linear chains L_4 , L_9 , L_{19} , For C_{60} and C_{72} ($N=1$), the weighted linear chain obtained from the generic graph has four vertices, each of weight -1 . Hence eigenspectra of IPR C_{60} and C_{72} contain $-1 \pm \phi$, $-1 \pm 1/\phi$ (i.e. 0.618 , -2.618 , -1.618 , -0.382) as eigenvalues. It has already been found that L_4 , L_9 , L_{19} , have L_4 as fragment. Now,

for L_9 : $N = 6$, $50+10N = 110$; $60+12N = 132$,
for L_{19} : $N = 16$, $50+10N = 210$; $60+12N = 252$,

for L_{39} : $N = 36$, $50+10N = 410$; $60+12N = 492$, and so on.

Hence the corresponding fullerenes i.e. C_{110} , C_{132} , C_{210} , C_{252} , C_{410} , C_{492} ,, all contain as eigenvalues the \pm pairs of the golden ratio and its conjugate, each incremented by -1 .

Fig. 11. Some special cases of π -systems having the golden ratio in their eigenspectra.

Some special cases

Many π -systems other than the ones mentioned above may have the golden ratio eigenvalues, some of which are shown in Fig. 11. Each of methylene cyclopentadiene and [3]radialene has two eigenvalues $-\varphi$ and $+1/\varphi$. Tetramethylene cyclohexane has four eigenvalues $\pm\varphi$, $\pm 1/\varphi$. The fourth graph in Fig. 11 has two L_4 fragments with uniform vertex

weights of $+1$ and -1 respectively; accordingly, the eight eigenvalues are $\pm 1 \pm \varphi$, $\pm 1 \pm 1/\varphi$. Another interesting system is the zwitterionic molecule, calicene, which has a mirrorplane fragment G_1 with $h = -2$, and two of its eigenvalues are φ , $1/\varphi$ ²⁶.

Concluding remark

Butadiene is the smallest possible real π -system having exactly the \pm pairs of the golden ratio and its

conjugate as eigenvalues. Other π -systems having such eigenvalues have molecular graphs from which the butadiene graph can be obtained as a mirror plane fragment. Some systems yield the 2-vertex graph G_2 as fragment and they have ϕ , $1/\phi$ (or ϕ , $1/\phi$) as two eigenvalues.

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